

Helmholtz Representations and Minimal Potentials: Differential Identities and Gauge Relations

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Abstract

We reformulate the Helmholtz theorem in terms of minimal potentials and of the differential identities that arise naturally from its structure. This approach is applied to time-dependent scalar fields and to dynamical vector fields, yielding Helmholtz-type representations with well-defined minimal potentials. In this formulation, the associated potentials satisfy decoupled wave equations in the minimal gauge and admit generalized gauge transformations. The framework is further extended to pairs of coupled vector fields through the Kapuścik representation and applied to macroscopic electrodynamics for the fields (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H}) , where the induced gauge relations reproduce Maxwell's differential combinations and the Lorenz condition as an expression of the minimal gauge.

In memory of Professor Manuel Aguirre (UCV)

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I INTRODUCTION

The classical Helmholtz theorem is one of the most fundamental results in vector analysis. It states that any regular vector field defined over a simply connected region of Euclidean space can be uniquely decomposed into a longitudinal (irrotational) part and a transverse (solenoidal) part. Originally formulated in integral form —relating the field directly to its sources[1-10]— this representation has been extensively presented and applied in electrostatics, magnetostatics, acoustics, and fluid dynamics as an essential tool for linking physical fields to their sources.

Although it was initially believed that the theorem was not applicable to causally time-dependent fields, over the years several authors have proposed dynamic generalizations incorporating causal retardations and even extensions involving an antisymmetric rank-two tensor in M^4 Minkowski space.[11-14] In this context belong the contributions of E. Kapuścik [15] (1984), M. Aguirre [16-18] and J.A. Heras, [19-21] who introduced dynamic formulations and gauge invariances for pairs of Maxwell-type coupled vector fields, with applications to classical and macroscopic electrodynamics in material media. Nevertheless, much of the literature has primarily emphasized the integral form of the Helmholtz theorem, being less inclined to employ explicit potentials, their associated wave equations, and the systematic exploration of their gauge structure.

In the approach developed by M. Aguirre [22] and continued in the present work, the Helmholtz theorem is understood from a distinct standpoint: the associated potentials and their gauge freedom form the conceptual core of the representation. Under this view, in

the static case a regular vector field $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ defined in a simply connected region of Euclidean space, decomposes uniquely as

$$\mathbf{F} = -\nabla\phi + \nabla \times \mathbf{A}, \quad (1)$$

where the associated potentials $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x})$ are determined from the differential equations

$$\nabla^2\phi = -\mathcal{D}, \quad \nabla^2\mathbf{A} = -\mathcal{C} + \nabla\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}, \quad (2)$$

with $\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{x}) := \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathcal{C}(\mathbf{x}) := \nabla \times \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ being the sources of the field $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})$ at each point \mathbf{x} of the region considered. However, since the divergence $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}$ does not contribute to the field, its gradient constitutes a “gauge source” which, once chosen arbitrarily, converts the second equation into a genuine Poisson equation.[2]. In particular, the simplest choice —vanishing divergence, analogous to the Coulomb gauge in electrostatics— will be called here the “minimal gauge.” This choice reproduces the differential identity satisfied by the “minimal potential”

$$\mathbf{A}_o(\mathbf{x}) := \frac{1}{4\pi} \nabla \times \int_V dV' \frac{\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}')}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|}, \quad (3)$$

that is, $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_o \equiv 0$, which, together with the scalar potential

$$\phi_o(\mathbf{x}) := \frac{1}{4\pi} \nabla \cdot \int_V dV' \frac{\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}')}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|}, \quad (4)$$

also determines the field through representation (1) and satisfy⁷ the Poisson equation (2).

It should be noted that the potentials (ϕ, \mathbf{A}) are related to the minimal ones (ϕ_o, \mathbf{A}_o) by the gauge transformations

$$\phi_o \rightarrow \phi = \phi_o + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{G}, \quad \mathbf{A}_o \rightarrow \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}_o - \nabla\gamma + \nabla \times \mathbf{G}, \quad (5)$$

where $\gamma(\mathbf{x})$ is an arbitrary gauge function, and $\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{x})$ is any harmonic solution to Laplace’s equation. Thus, the arbitrariness of the vector potential corresponds to the gauge freedom for $\gamma(\mathbf{x})$, as it follows immediately from the second Eq. (5) that $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = -\nabla^2\gamma$. If we require all potentials to be set in the “minimal gauge” $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = 0$, then $\gamma(\mathbf{x})$ must necessarily be harmonic.

This viewpoint —focused on minimal potentials, the differential identities they satisfy, and the associated gauge structure—is not the conventional one in the literature, but it provides a clear conceptual framework for better understanding the extension of the Helmholtz theorem to new domains [14, 23-26]. On this basis it is possible to extend Helmholtz-type representations for previously known time-dependent scalar and vector fields, formulating them in terms of retarded minimal potentials and general gauge transformations of the associated potentials that leave the fields invariant. This will be the guiding theme of the following sections.

Sections II and III develop this perspective for static scalar fields and time-dependent vector fields, introducing their minimal potentials, the corresponding identities, and the associated differential equations. Section IV extends the formalism to two coupled vector fields through the Kapuścik representation. Section V presents an application to the macroscopic pair (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H}) in electrodynamics, while Section VI addresses the dynamic scalar field and its inverse formulation. Finally, selected physical applications of pedagogical interest—including macroscopic electrodynamics itself—are discussed to illustrate the structural scope of the approach.

II GENERALIZED HELMHOLTZ THEOREM FOR VECTOR FIELDS.

Following a brief review of the classical Helmholtz theorem —framed from an approach centered on minimal potentials and the associated gauge relation— we now turn to the corresponding formulation for time-dependent vector fields.

It is useful to recall how the generalized Helmholtz theorem for dynamic —or causally time-dependent— vector fields has been formulated in various ways by different authors. [20-26]

While most of these formulations have focused mainly on the integral decomposition of the field from its sources, our approach emphasizes the retarded Helmholtz potentials as fields that satisfy inhomogeneous wave equations under specific constraint and gauge conditions, together with the general transformations that leave the field invariant.[22]

Indeed, if $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x},t)$ is a regular vector field defined at every point \mathbf{x} and instant t in a simply connected domain $V \subset \mathbb{R}^3$, propagating hyperbolically in vacuum at the speed of light c , it can be decomposed into three components: a longitudinal component, a transverse component, and a third component referred to as the temporal component [27] [using the notation $c^{-1}\partial_t := (1/c) \partial/\partial t$]

$$\mathbf{F} = -\nabla\phi_o + \nabla \times \mathbf{A}_o + c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{K}_o, \quad (6)$$

where the associated minimal potentials satisfy the following differentials identities:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_o \equiv 0, \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{K}_o - c^{-1}\partial_t\phi_o \equiv 0, \quad \nabla \times \mathbf{K}_o - c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{A}_o \equiv \mathbf{0}, \quad (7)$$

which are consistent with the definitions of the retarded minimal potentials

$$\phi_o = \frac{1}{4\pi} \nabla \cdot \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathbf{F}']}{R}; \quad (8a)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_o = \frac{1}{4\pi} \nabla \times \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathbf{F}']}{R}, \quad \mathbf{K}_o = \frac{1}{4\pi} c^{-1}\partial_t \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathbf{F}']}{R}, \quad (8b)$$

where the bracketed notation $[\mathbf{F}']$ means evaluation of the field $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is evaluated at the retarded time $t_r = t - R/c$ and at the source point $\mathbf{x}' \in V$; that is, $[\mathbf{F}'] \equiv \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}', t_r)$. This notation is extended to any other retarded field or to any linear operator \mathcal{O} , so that $[\mathcal{O}'] \equiv \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{x}', t_r)$, understanding that, whenever \mathcal{O} involves spatial differential operators, these act on the source coordinates.

From representation (6) and the null identities (7), the wave equation associated with the three potentials can be derived directly. Indeed, by defining the abbreviations: $\mathcal{D}_{A_o} := \nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_o$, $L_{K_o} := \nabla \cdot \mathbf{K}_o - c^{-1}\partial_t\phi_o$, $\mathcal{W}_o := \nabla \times \mathbf{K}_o - c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{A}_o$, and taking, respectively, the divergence, the curl, and the time derivate of (6), one obtains, after rearranging the spatial and temporal terms so as to bring out the d'Alembertian operator $\square := \nabla^2 - c^{-2}\partial^2/\partial t^2$, the expressions

$$\square\phi_o = -\mathcal{D}_F + c^{-1}\partial_t L_{K_o}; \quad (9a)$$

$$\square\mathbf{A}_o = -\mathcal{C}_F + \nabla\mathcal{D}_{A_o} + c^{-1}\partial_t\mathcal{W}_o, \quad \square\mathbf{K} = -\mathcal{J}_F + \nabla L_{K_o} - \nabla \times \mathcal{W}_o, \quad (9b)$$

where we specify the field sources in the form

$$\mathcal{D}_F := \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}, \quad \mathcal{C}_F := \nabla \times \mathbf{F}, \quad \mathcal{J}_F := c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{F}, \quad (10)$$

given throughout the region. But since \mathcal{D}_{A_o} , L_{K_o} and \mathbf{W}_o vanish identically by (7), the differential equations (9) reduce to the inhomogeneous wave equations

$$\square\phi_o = -\mathcal{D}_F, \quad \square\mathbf{A}_o = -\mathcal{C}_F, \quad \square\mathbf{K}_o = -\mathcal{J}_F. \quad (11)$$

However, we must note that the potentials ϕ_o , \mathbf{A}_o y \mathbf{K}_o are not unique, since from them one can construct a family of new potentials through the following gauge transformations, where, for compactness of notation, the index $a=1,2$ is introduced so that $\mathbf{A}_1 := \mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{A}_2 := \mathbf{K}$, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_o &\rightarrow \phi = \phi_o + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{G}_2 - c^{-1}\partial_t\Omega_2; \\ \mathbf{A}_{oa} &\rightarrow \mathbf{A}_a = \mathbf{A}_{oa} - \nabla\Omega_a + \varepsilon_{ab}\nabla \times \mathbf{G}_b + c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{G}_a, \end{aligned}$$

where Ω_1 , Ω_2 and \mathbf{G}_1 are arbitrary functions, and the two-dimensional antisymmetric Levi-Civita tensor ε_{ab} has been introduced (with $\varepsilon_{12}=+1$). In these transformations, $\mathbf{G}_2(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is any solution of the homogeneous wave equation $\square\mathbf{G}_2 = \mathbf{0}$, such that it leaves the field invariant according to $\mathbf{F} \rightarrow \mathbf{F} + \square\mathbf{G}_2$, i.e.:

$$\mathbf{F} = -\nabla\phi + \nabla \times \mathbf{A} + c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{K}. \quad (12)$$

Now, unlike the differentials identities (7), the constraints between the new potentials manifest themselves through the residual gauge:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_A &:= \nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = -\square\Omega_1 + c^{-1}\partial_t(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{G}_1 - c^{-1}\partial_t\Omega_1); \\ L_K &:= \nabla \cdot \mathbf{K} - c^{-1}\partial_t\phi = -\square\Omega_2; \\ \mathbf{W} &:= \nabla \times \mathbf{K} - c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{A} = +\square\mathbf{G}_1 - \nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{G}_1 - c^{-1}\partial_t\Omega_1), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

which act as gauge sources in the inhomogeneous wave equations:

$$\square\phi = -\mathcal{D}_F + c^{-1}\partial_tL_K; \quad (14a)$$

$$\square\mathbf{A} = -\mathcal{C}_F + \nabla\mathcal{D}_A + c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{W}, \quad \square\mathbf{K} = -\mathcal{J}_F + \nabla L_K - \nabla \times \mathbf{W}. \quad (14b)$$

These inhomogeneous wave equations, satisfied by the new potentials, are directly obtained from the Helmholtz decomposition (12) together with the source terms as defined in (10).

On the other hand, (Theorem of the "minimal gauge"), *the particular choice*:

$$\mathcal{D}_A = 0, \quad L_K = 0, \quad \mathbf{W} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (15)$$

which reproduces the structure of the differentials identities (7), defines the calibration of the potentials in the minimal gauge. For this, it is necessary that the functions (Ω_1 , Ω_2 , \mathbf{G}_1) satisfy the equations $\square\Omega_1 = \square\Omega_2 = 0$, together with the coupling condition $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{G}_1 = c^{-1}\partial_t\Omega_1$, while \mathbf{G}_1 must also satisfy the homogeneous wave equation $\square\mathbf{G}_1 = \mathbf{0}$. With this, the remaining gauge freedom is eliminated, and the differential equations (14) reduce to the inhomogeneous wave equation of the same form as Eqs. (9), now written for $(\phi, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{K})$, ensuring that the potentials are free of arbitrary contributions. In any case, if we want the potentials $(\phi, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{K})$ to be defined throughout space, along with the minimal gauge, and with a rapid decay of all fields as $|\mathbf{x}| \rightarrow \infty$, certain conditions must be fulfilled to guarantee the uniqueness of the field $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, t)$.

On the one hand, the wave equations (9) admit, for the new potentials $(\phi, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{K})$, the retarded solutions of the form:

$$\phi = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{D}'_F]}{R}; \quad (16a)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{C}'_F]}{R}, \quad \mathbf{K} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{J}'_F]}{R}, \quad (16b)$$

which are valid if the decay conditions for the surface fields \mathbf{F}_S are applied at spatial infinity.

On the other hand, it must necessarily follow that the gauge functions Ω_a, \mathbf{G}_a vanish under the same spatial decay, yielding $\mathcal{D}_A = L_K = 0$ and $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{0}$, thereby removing all global homogeneous contributions.

Additionally, it is necessary to impose initial temporal conditions that ensure the physical coherence of the system: sources and potentials must vanish before an initial instant t_0 and remain regular in their temporal evolution, thus guaranteeing the hyperbolic behavior and causal consistency of the retarded solutions, free of residual contributions from the infinite past. [28]

Under these conditions —spatial decay, boundary elimination, minimal gauge fixation, and initial temporal regular— the set of potentials that satisfy Eqs. (9) and reproduce the field \mathbf{F} through Eq. (12) are precisely the minimal potentials $\phi = \phi_o, \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}_o, \mathbf{K} = \mathbf{K}_o$.

We can therefore state the following

Corollary. *The retarded potentials $(\phi_o, \mathbf{A}_o, \mathbf{K}_o)$ which determine the time-dependent vector field \mathbf{F} , are the only potentials calibrated in the minimal gauge throughout the entire space.*

III KAPUŚCIK REPRESENTATION AND GAUGE INVARIANCE OF MACROSCOPIC ELECTRODYNAMICS

A causal generalization of the Helmholtz theorem for two time-dependent vector fields was developed by Edward Kapaściik [15] in 1984-85, and later (1922) analyzed by the present author [22] and more recently by J. A. Heras and R. Heras [21] in 2020. This formulation has been applied to both microscopic and macroscopic Maxwell electromagnetic equations.

We present it here by deriving it from the Helmholtz decompositions of each individual field $\mathbf{F}_a(\mathbf{x}, t)$ (with $a=1,2$) of the form (12), emphasizing the coupling between the vector sources: namely, the temporal source of one field with the spatial source of the other, developed through the conjugation of their minimal potentials under internal gauge conditions.

Indeed, given the Helmholtz representation for each individual field $\mathbf{F}_a(\mathbf{x}, t)$

$$\mathbf{F}_a = -\nabla\phi_a + \nabla \times \mathbf{A}_a + c^{-1}\partial_t \mathbf{K}_a, \quad (17)$$

where the potentials $(\phi_a, \mathbf{A}_a, \mathbf{K}_a)$ are calibrated in their minimal gauge (over all space), if we couple to each field the differential vector identity (15)

$$\mathbf{W}_a := \nabla \times \mathbf{K}_a - c^{-1}\partial_t \mathbf{A}_a = \mathbf{0}, \quad (18)$$

which preserves gauge invariance of the field in the form

$$\mathbf{F}_a \rightarrow \mathbf{F}_a - \varepsilon_{ab}\mathbf{W}_b, \quad (19)$$

one may define the internal link between potentials as

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_a := -\varepsilon_{ab}\mathbf{A}_b - \mathbf{K}_a, \quad (20)$$

after factoring the corresponding derivatives. In this way, the pair $\mathbf{F}_1(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\mathbf{F}_2(\mathbf{x}, t)$ adopts the coupled structure expressed by Kapuścik's representation

$$\mathbf{F}_a = -\nabla\varphi_a + \varepsilon_{ab}\nabla \times \mathbf{\Gamma}_b - c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{F}_a, \quad (21)$$

a dual decomposition valid in particular for the retarded minimal potentials

$$\varphi_{oa} = \nabla \cdot \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[\mathbf{F}'_a]}{R}; \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_{oa} = -\varepsilon_{ab}\nabla \times \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[\mathbf{F}'_b]}{R} - \frac{1}{4\pi}c^{-1}\partial_t \int dV' \frac{[\mathbf{F}'_a]}{R}, \quad (23)$$

which, as such, satisfy directly the minimal Lorenz-type differential identities

$$L_{oa} := \nabla \cdot \mathbf{\Gamma}_{oa} + c^{-1}\partial_t\varphi_{oa} \equiv 0. \quad (24)$$

Consequently, upon evaluating expressions (23) and (24) by integration by parts over all space, under the usual decay conditions at infinity, the corresponding potentials adopt the form

$$\varphi_{oa} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}_a)']}{R}; \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_{oa} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[(-\varepsilon_{ab}\nabla \times \mathbf{F}_b - c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{F}_a)']}{R}, \quad (26)$$

where the scalar and vector sources of the generalized Helmholtz fields $\mathbf{F}_a(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are specified by

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}_a := \varrho_a, \quad -\varepsilon_{ab}\nabla \times \mathbf{F}_b - c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{F}_a := \mathbf{J}_a, \quad (27)$$

thereby fixing explicitly the causal form of the minimal potentials in Kapuścik's representation in terms of the effective retarded sources.

Moreover, it is worth noting that the differential definitions in (27) automatically imply the continuity equations

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_a + c^{-1}\partial_t\varrho_a = 0, \quad (29)$$

which follow directly from the coupled differential structure of the generalized Helmholtz theorem together with Kapuścik's representation.

In the context of macroscopic electrodynamics, and considering the generalized Helmholtz theorem for two coupled fields, the electromagnetic field may be described through one of four field pairs: $\{(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}), (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H}), (\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{H}), (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{B})\}$. Among these, the second and third pairs are the most interesting, because in both cases two scalar and two vector potentials appear, together with a broad gauge invariance that is both appealing and internally consistent. Regarding the pair (\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{H}) previous analyses exist within this framework [22, 23, 29]. Here, however, we focus on the pair (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H}) .

Indeed, consider a simple material medium occupying an arbitrary volume region V , characterized by a polarization $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and a magnetization $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. Both vector quantities are assumed to be known at every point $\mathbf{x} \in V$ and at every time t , and vanishing outside that region. If electric charge and conduction current densities, denoted ρ_e and \mathbf{J}_e , are

present in the medium, the electromagnetic field in V may be described in terms of the electric displacement $\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and the magnetic field intensity $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. Now, using Kapuścik's representation and setting in Eq. (19): $\mathbf{F}_1 = \varepsilon_o^{-1}\mathbf{D}$ and $\mathbf{F}_2 = -\mu_o c\mathbf{H}$, together with the specific identifications: $\varphi_1 = \phi$, $\varphi_2 = -(\varepsilon_o c)^{-1}\psi$, $\mathbf{F}_1 = c\mathbf{A}$, $\mathbf{F}_2 = -\varepsilon_o^{-1}\mathbf{\Lambda}$, we obtain the decompositions

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{D} &= -\varepsilon_o \nabla \phi - \nabla \times \mathbf{\Lambda} - \varepsilon_o \partial_t \mathbf{A}, \\ \mathbf{H} &= -\nabla \psi + \mu_o^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{A} - \partial_t \mathbf{\Lambda},\end{aligned}\tag{30}$$

valid in particular for the minimal potentials [see Eqs. (22)-(23)], given in compact form in terms of the auxiliary fields $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_e$ and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_m$:

$$\phi_o = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_e, \quad \mathbf{A}_o = \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}_m - c^{-2} \partial_t \boldsymbol{\alpha}_e,\tag{31}$$

$$\psi_o = \mu_o^{-1} \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_m, \quad \mathbf{\Lambda}_o = -\varepsilon_o (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}_e + \partial_t \boldsymbol{\alpha}_m),\tag{32}$$

defined through the Helmholtz integrals over all space given in Eq. (87). These minimal potentials, as such, automatically satisfy the general minimal identity $L_{oa} \equiv 0$ from Eq. (24), and consequently directly fulfill the minimal Lorenz-type constraints:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}_o + \varepsilon_o \mu_o \partial_t \phi_o \equiv 0, \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{\Lambda}_o + \varepsilon_o \mu_o \partial_t \psi_o \equiv 0.\tag{33}$$

Upon considering the previously established electromagnetic identification, the Kapuścik expressions (25)–(26) lead to the retarded functional forms of the minimal potentials associated with the pair (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H}) :

$$\phi_o = \frac{1}{4\pi\varepsilon_o} \int dV' \frac{[(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D})']}{R}, \quad \psi_o = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{H})']}{R};\tag{34}$$

$$\mathbf{A}_o = \frac{\mu_o}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[(\nabla \times \mathbf{H} - \partial_t \mathbf{D})']}{R};\tag{35}$$

$$\mathbf{\Lambda}_o = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[(\nabla \times \mathbf{D} + c^{-2} \partial_t \mathbf{H})']}{R}.\tag{36}$$

in which the macroscopic differential combinations appear explicitly; potentials that can alternatively be obtained by integrating by parts the representations (31)–(32).

In this context, the quantities ϱ_a and \mathbf{J}_a and defined in (27)—which arise directly from (25)–(26)—acquire their macroscopic physical meaning upon specifying: $\varrho_1 = \varepsilon_o^{-1}\rho_e$, $\varrho_2 = \mu_o c \nabla \cdot \mathbf{M}$; $\mathbf{J}_1 = \mu_o c \mathbf{J}_e$, $\mathbf{J}_2 = -\mathbf{I}_m$. Indeed, substituting these expressions into (27) for \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{H} , and using the constitutive relations of the medium, $\mathbf{D} = \varepsilon_o \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{P}$ and $\mathbf{H} = \mu_o^{-1} \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{M}$, one obtains the macroscopic system [28]

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_e, \quad \nabla \times \mathbf{H} - \partial_t \mathbf{D} = \mathbf{J}_e,\tag{37a}$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{H} = \mu_o^{-1} \zeta_m, \quad \nabla \times \mathbf{D} + \varepsilon_o \mu_o \partial_t \mathbf{H} = -\varepsilon_o \mathbf{I}_m,\tag{37b}$$

whose bound, or “fictitious” sources [30] associated with $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ correspond to the magnetic charge density and the polarization–magnetization current density:

$$\zeta_m := -\mu_o \nabla \cdot \mathbf{M}, \quad \mathbf{I}_m := -\varepsilon_o^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{P} + \mu_o \partial_t \mathbf{M},\tag{38}$$

and, together with (ρ_e, \mathbf{J}_e) , satisfy the continuity equations:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_e + \partial_t \rho_e = 0, \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{I}_m + \partial_t \zeta_m = 0.\tag{39}$$

On the other hand, starting from Eqs. (30), and taking into account the Maxwell equations (37) together with Eqs. (33), it is straightforward to verify that the minimal potentials satisfy the inhomogeneous wave equations

$$\square\phi_o = -\varepsilon_o^{-1}\rho_e, \quad \square\mathbf{A}_o = -\mu_o\mathbf{J}_e, \quad (40a)$$

$$\square\psi_o = -\mu_o^{-1}\zeta_m, \quad \square\mathbf{\Lambda}_o = -\varepsilon_o\mathbf{I}_m. \quad (40b)$$

As in the case of a single field $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, the minimal potentials are not the only ones that reproduce the fields (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H}) : there exists a family of potentials related to them via Kapuścik gauge transformations that leave the form (30) invariant. These transformations take the form

$$\phi = \phi_o + \varepsilon_o^{-1}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{G} - \partial_t\Omega, \quad (41)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}_o + \nabla\Omega + \nabla \times \mathbf{W} - \mu_o\partial_t\mathbf{G},$$

$$\psi = \psi_o + \mu_o^{-1}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{W} - \partial_t\chi, \quad (42)$$

$$\mathbf{\Lambda} = \mathbf{\Lambda}_o + \nabla\chi - \nabla \times \mathbf{G} - \varepsilon_o\partial_t\mathbf{W},$$

where \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{W} are solutions of the homogeneous wave equations $\square\mathbf{G}=\square\mathbf{W}=\mathbf{0}$, while Ω and χ are arbitrary functions that allow the Lorenz-gauge constraints to be expressed as:

$$L_A := \nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} + \varepsilon_o\mu_o\partial_t\phi = \square\Omega, \quad L_\Lambda := \nabla \cdot \mathbf{\Lambda} + \varepsilon_o\mu_o\partial_t\psi_o = \square\chi. \quad (43)$$

These latter functions, Ω and χ , do not modify the fields, but they fix the constraints, Eq. (43), which act as ‘‘gauge sources’’ in the wave equations

$$\square\phi = -\varepsilon_o^{-1}\rho_e - \partial_tL_A, \quad \square\mathbf{A} = -\mu_o\mathbf{J}_e + \nabla L_A, \quad (44a)$$

$$\square\psi = -\mu_o^{-1}\zeta_m - \partial_tL_\Lambda, \quad \square\mathbf{\Lambda} = -\varepsilon_o\mathbf{I}_m + \nabla L_\Lambda, \quad (44b)$$

which are satisfied by the transformed potentials.

Of course, to calibrate them in the minimal Lorenz gauge, which reproduces the structure of the differentials identities given in Eq. (33), it is sufficient to require in (43) $\square\Omega = \square\chi = 0$, thereby reducing Eqs. (44) to the decoupled wave Eqs. (40) for $(\phi, \mathbf{A}, \psi, \mathbf{\Lambda})$.

It is interesting to note that, in the absence of macroscopic material media, i.e., for $\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{0}$, the choice of associated potentials $\psi = 0$ and $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \mathbf{0}$ is consistent with particular solution $\chi = 0$ of the second of Eqs. (42), and $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{W} = \mathbf{0}$ of their corresponding homogeneous wave equations, along with the vanishing of the transformations equations (60). This implies that the representation (30) of the fields (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H}) written in terms of the new potentials, reduces to the familiar expressions

$$\mathbf{D} = \varepsilon_o(-\nabla\phi - \partial_t\mathbf{A}), \quad \mathbf{H} = \mu_o^{-1}\nabla \times \mathbf{A}, \quad (45)$$

$$\phi = \phi_o - \partial_t\Omega_A, \quad \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}_o + \nabla\Omega_A. \quad (46)$$

IV TIME-DEPENDENT (RETARDED) SCALAR FIELD

After having described the Helmholtz theorem in the dynamical domain of time-dependent vector fields and their gauge transformations, and after examining its extended formulation for two ‘‘Maxwell-type’’ coupled fields in the sense of Kapuścik-Heras, it is

natural to ask whether an analogous construction can be established for a scalar field that depends causally on time.

In this section, we address this question by developing a formulation for a scalar field $\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ consistent with the hyperbolic regime, involving retarded sources and a minimal gauge distinct from those usually associated with vector fields, together with the gauge transformations that are necessary and sufficient for the corresponding potentials.

Starting from the identical space-time distributional representation for a dynamic scalar field $\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t)$, defined within a volume region $V \subset \mathbb{R}^3$,

$$\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int_V dV' \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt' \varphi(\mathbf{x}', t') \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') \delta(t - t'), \quad (47)$$

and introducing the retarded Green function $G_r(\mathbf{x}, t; \mathbf{x}', t')$ which satisfies the singular d'Alembert wave equation,

$$\square G_r(\mathbf{x}, t; \mathbf{x}', t') = -4\pi \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') \delta(t - t'), \quad (48)$$

where

$$G_r(\mathbf{x}, t; \mathbf{x}', t') = \frac{\delta(t' - [t - R/c])}{R}, \quad (49)$$

one obtains physical meaning by introducing causality through the evaluation of all quantities at the retarded time $t_r = t - R/c$, with $R = |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|$. Thus, substituting Eqs. (48) and (49) into Eq. (47), and applying the properties of the Dirac delta, we obtain

$$\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \square \int_V dV' \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt' \varphi(\mathbf{x}', t') \delta(t' - t_r)/R, \quad (50)$$

and after performing the time integral, this becomes

$$\varphi = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \square \int_V dV' \frac{[\varphi']}{R}, \quad (51)$$

the retarded integral representation of the field φ .

Developing the d'Alembert operator, the expression separates naturally into its spatial and temporal components:

$$\varphi = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \nabla^2 \int_V dV' \frac{[\varphi']}{R} + \frac{1}{4\pi c^2} \partial_{tt} \int_V dV' \frac{[\varphi']}{R}, \quad (52)$$

which can be written more compactly as

$$\varphi = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{Z}_o + c^{-1} \partial_t \Omega_o, \quad (53)$$

upon defining the fields

$$\mathbf{Z}_o = \frac{1}{4\pi} \nabla \int_V dV' \frac{[\varphi']}{R}, \quad \Omega_o = \frac{1}{4\pi} c^{-1} \partial_t \int_V dV' \frac{[\varphi']}{R}, \quad (54)$$

which immediately satisfy the identities

$$\mathbf{C}_{oZ} := \nabla \times \mathbf{Z}_o \equiv \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{V}_{o\Omega} := \nabla \Omega_o - c^{-1} \partial_t \mathbf{Z}_o \equiv \mathbf{0}. \quad (55)$$

We can therefore formulate the following:

Theorem: *Every regular time-dependent scalar field φ defined on a simply connected region of \mathbb{R}^3 can be represented in terms of the divergence of a vector field and the time derivative of a scalar field, called the minimal potentials of the scalar field, if they verify the identities (55). These potentials are obtained through retarded integrals equivalent to*

the convolutions of φ with the gradient and the time derivative, respectively, of the retarded Green's kernel G_r of the d'Alembert operator, considering φ null outside V .

On the other hand, if we specify the functions

$$\mathcal{G}_\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t) := \nabla\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad \mathcal{T}_\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t) := c^{-1}\partial_t\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (56)$$

and we apply the gradient and the time derivative to representation (53), we obtain, respectively, the expressions

$$\mathcal{G}_\varphi = -\nabla\nabla\cdot\mathbf{Z}_o + c^{-1}\nabla\partial_t\Omega_o, \quad \mathcal{T}_\varphi = -c^{-1}\partial_t\nabla\cdot\mathbf{Z}_o + c^{-2}\partial_{tt}\Omega_o, \quad (57)$$

and these, in turn, can be written—using the wave operator—in the equivalent form

$$\square\mathbf{Z}_o = -\mathcal{G}_\varphi - \nabla\times\mathbf{C}_{oZ} + c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{V}_{o\Omega}, \quad \square\Omega_o = -\mathcal{T}_\varphi + \nabla\cdot\mathbf{V}_{o\Omega}, \quad (58)$$

which reduce to the inhomogeneous wave equations

$$\square\mathbf{Z}_o = -\mathcal{G}_\varphi, \quad \square\Omega_o = -\mathcal{T}_\varphi, \quad (59)$$

if we take into account the null identities (55).

Now, according to our extended Helmholtz formulation applied in this work, we may also generalize the concept of potentials for this scalar field, taking as a basis the decomposition (53) together with the differential equations they satisfy. Within this framework, we state the following second

Theorem: Let $\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ be a regular scalar field defined on a simply connected region of \mathbb{R}^3 . Then there exist regular fields $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\Omega(\mathbf{x}, t)$, called the potentials associated with φ , if and only if they determine it through:

$$\varphi = -\nabla\cdot\mathbf{Z} + c^{-1}\partial_t\Omega, \quad (60)$$

and satisfy the differential equations

$$\square\mathbf{Z} = -\mathcal{G}_\varphi - \nabla\times\mathbf{C}_Z + c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{V}_\Omega, \quad \square\Omega = -\mathcal{T}_\varphi + \nabla\cdot\mathbf{V}_\Omega, \quad (61)$$

where the functions (56) are the sources of the field specified throughout the region, while the constraints

$$\mathbf{C}_Z = \nabla\times\mathbf{Z}, \quad \mathbf{V}_\Omega = \nabla\Omega - c^{-1}\partial_t\mathbf{Z}, \quad (62)$$

(which do not contribute to the field) enter in Eqs. (51) as gauge sources and must be chosen arbitrarily (longitudinal gauge [26]). Once such a choice is made, Eqs. (61) represent genuine inhomogeneous wave equations. Conversely, any pair (\mathbf{Z}, Ω) that satisfies Eqs. (60) and (61) for some choice of \mathbf{C}_Z and \mathbf{V}_Ω reproduces the same φ .

Indeed, inserting Eq. (60) into definitions (56) yields an expression analogous to Eq. (57), and applying the d'Alembert operator then leads to Eqs. (61). At this point, it is worth recalling that the minimal potentials (\mathbf{Z}_o, Ω_o) satisfy by definition the identities (55), from which we can obtain—as sufficient conditions—the associated potentials (\mathbf{Z}, Ω) through the gauge transformations:

$$\Omega = \Omega_o - \nabla\cdot\tilde{\mathbf{Q}} - c^{-1}\partial_t\tilde{\omega}, \quad \mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{Z}_o - \nabla\tilde{\omega} + \nabla\times\tilde{\mathbf{W}} - c^{-1}\partial_t\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}, \quad (63)$$

where the regular gauge functions $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are arbitrary, while $\tilde{\omega}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is any solution of the wave equation $\square\tilde{\omega} = 0$, ensuring the invariance of the representation (60).

Now, unlike the nullity of the differential identities (55), the constraints of the pair (\mathbf{Z}, Ω) that reproduce them remain arbitrary and satisfy the expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{V}_\Omega &= -\square \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} - \nabla \times (\nabla \times \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} + c^{-1} \partial_t \tilde{\mathbf{W}}), \\
\mathbf{C}_Z &= -\square \tilde{\mathbf{W}} + \nabla \nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{W}} - c^{-1} \partial_t (\nabla \times \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} + c^{-1} \partial_t \tilde{\mathbf{W}}).
\end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

In particular, if we require that (\mathbf{Z}, Ω) be calibrated in the minimal gauge $\mathbf{C}_Z = \mathbf{V}_\Omega = \mathbf{0}$, just a (\mathbf{Z}_o, Ω_o) , we may choose $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ so that they satisfy the wave equations $\square \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} = \square \tilde{\mathbf{W}} = \mathbf{0}$; and simultaneously $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}$ verifies the condition $\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{W}} = 0$, together with its coupled temporal derivative $c^{-1} \partial \tilde{\mathbf{W}} / \partial t = -\nabla \times \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}$, respectively.

Having established the transformations (63) as sufficient conditions ensuring the invariance of the field φ , we now show that they are also necessary conditions when considering the inversion of this theorem.[17, 18] For this purpose, we address the problem of finding all pairs (\mathbf{Z}, Ω) for which the representation (60) is satisfied, assuming the field φ is given at every point $\mathbf{x} \in V$ and instant $t > t_o$, considering the functions \mathbf{C}_Z and \mathbf{V}_Ω arbitrarily chosen in this volume, while the boundary conditions are established by specifying the functions:

$$\Omega_S(\mathbf{x}, t) := \Omega(\mathbf{x}, t)|_{\mathbf{x} \in S}, \quad \mathbf{Z}_S(\mathbf{x}, t) := \mathbf{Z}(\mathbf{x}, t)|_{\mathbf{x} \in S}, \tag{65}$$

also chosen arbitrarily.

Applying representation (60) to the scalar field $\Omega(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and the hyperbolic Helmholtz decomposition (6) to the vector field $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, both regular, we obtain the identities

$$\Omega = (-\nabla \cdot \nabla + c^{-2} \partial_{tt}) \int_V dV' \frac{[\Omega']}{4\pi R}, \tag{66}$$

$$\mathbf{Z} = (-\nabla \nabla \cdot + \nabla \times \nabla \times + c^{-2} \partial_{tt}) \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathbf{Z}']}{4\pi R}. \tag{67}$$

By distributing and commuting the first-order space-time derivatives with the integral operator, and using the identities $\nabla \times ([\mathbf{Z}']/R) = [(\nabla \times \mathbf{Z})']/R - \nabla' \times ([\mathbf{Z}']/R)$, $\partial/\partial t [\mathbf{Z}'] = [(\partial \mathbf{Z}/\partial t)']$ (and analogously for Ω), together with representation (60), the choices (62) for \mathbf{C}_Z and \mathbf{V}_Ω and keeping the boundary terms, one obtains solutions of the form (63). In these, the gauge functions $(\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}, \tilde{\mathbf{W}}, \tilde{\omega})$ are explicitly given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathbf{V}'_\Omega]}{R} - \frac{1}{4\pi} \oint_S dS' \hat{\mathbf{n}} \frac{[\Omega'_S]}{R}, \tag{68}$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{W}} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathbf{C}'_Z]}{R} - \frac{1}{4\pi} \oint_S dS' \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \frac{[\mathbf{Z}'_S]}{R}, \tag{69}$$

$$\tilde{\omega} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \oint_S dS' \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \frac{[\mathbf{Z}'_S]}{R}. \tag{70}$$

The presence of the “longitudinal” constraint \mathbf{C}_Z and \mathbf{V}_Ω in the volume integrals makes evident the arbitrariness of the function $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}$, as well as that of the potentials \mathbf{Z} and Ω [see Eqs. (62) and (64) respectively]; likewise, it can be shown by direct calculation that the function $\tilde{\omega}$ given in Eq. (70) satisfies the homogeneous wave equation $\square \tilde{\omega} = 0$. In the most general case, if we want the minimal gauge to be valid throughout space, we can write the following

Corollary (Uniqueness of the Minimal Gauge): Under the hypotheses of regularity and decay conditions at least as fast as $1/|\mathbf{x}|^2$ as $|\mathbf{x}| \rightarrow \infty$, and null initial conditions in the distant past for all involved fields, we have:

i) the field $\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ admits at least one pair of potentials (\mathbf{Z}_o, Ω_o) globally validated in their “minimal” identities $\mathbf{C}_{o\mathbf{Z}} = \mathbf{V}_{o\Omega} = \mathbf{0}$ and satisfying the wave equations (59).

ii) If (\mathbf{Z}, Ω) is another pair that fulfills the same initial and decay conditions, satisfies the minimal gauge $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{Z}} = \mathbf{V}_{\Omega} = \mathbf{0}$ and the decoupled wave equations $\square\mathbf{Z} = -\mathcal{G}_{\varphi}$ and $\square\Omega = -\mathcal{T}_{\varphi}$, then $\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{Z}_o$ and $\Omega = \Omega_o$. In this framework, the only compatible choice of gauge functions in the Eqs. (64) is $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}} = \tilde{\mathbf{W}} = \mathbf{0}$, and $\tilde{\omega} = 0$, confirming the uniqueness of the scalar field and its corresponding gauge.

iii) The “minimal” potentials can be expressed in either of the two equivalent forms: a) in terms of the field φ , as in the definitions (54), or b) by applying the differential operators to the integrals in Eq. (44), using the identities $\nabla([\varphi']/R) = [(\nabla\varphi)']/R - \nabla'([\varphi']/R)$, $\partial/\partial t[\varphi'] = [(\partial\varphi/\partial t)']$ and inserting the sources defined in (56), resulting in:

$$\mathbf{Z}_o = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{G}'_{\varphi}]}{R}, \quad \Omega_o = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{T}'_{\varphi}]}{R}, \quad (71)$$

where the surface integral originating from the term $\nabla'([\varphi']/R)$ vanishes under the imposed spatial decay conditions.

An interesting illustrative case appears in electrodynamics when the scalar field of representation (60) is identified with $\varphi = \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{E}$; that is, with the rate at which the electric field does work on the current density (the local power density). Within this framework, the differential Poynting theorem, in the dynamical regime, establishes the energy balance law

$$-\nabla \cdot \mathbf{S} - \partial_t u = \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{E}, \quad (72)$$

where $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{H}$ is the Poynting vector (electromagnetic energy flux) and $u = (\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{H} \cdot \mathbf{B})/2$ is its associated energy density.[28]

Comparing representation (53) with the differential form (72), it is evident that the pair of potentials (\mathbf{Z}, Ω) can be identified with:

$$\mathbf{Z} \equiv \mathbf{S}, \quad \Omega \equiv -cu, \quad (73)$$

so that the Poynting vector and the energy density play the structural roles analogous to those potentials.

However, unlike the minimal potentials (\mathbf{Z}_o, Ω_o) , which by construction satisfy the identities $\mathbf{C}_{o\mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{V}_{ou} = \mathbf{0}$, the electromagnetic quantities \mathbf{S} and u do not fulfill these conditions. Indeed, by their physical definition \mathbf{S} is generally not curl-free, nor does the dynamical link between u and \mathbf{S} vanish. Thus, the pair $(\mathbf{S}, -cu)$ is not minimal in the sense of the present theorem. Accordingly, the functions $\mathbf{C}_{\mathbf{S}} = \nabla \times \mathbf{S}$ and $\mathbf{V}_u = -c(\nabla u + c^{-2} \partial \mathbf{S} / \partial t)$, which act as arbitrary gauge sources within the abstract framework of the theorem, become uniquely specified once the electromagnetic identification (73) is imposed; that is, they are determined by the underlying energy dynamics.

In this way, $(\mathbf{S}, -cu)$ defines a specific gauge within this representation, in which its associated potentials are directly related to the energy flux and density —a correspondence fixed by Maxwell’s equations and the Poynting theorem.

V APPLICATIONS

Having completed the general theoretical framework of the Helmholtz–type formalism for time-dependent scalar and vector fields, it is natural to explore a simple and concrete

physical application to test its consistency. We first consider the case of the gravitational field generated by a sphere of radius R_o , whose mass density decreases linearly with the radius until it vanishes at the boundary. This configuration allows us to illustrate how, in the regime static corresponding to the Newtonian limit $c \rightarrow \infty$, the minimal vector potential associated with a scalar field reconstructs accurately the classical exterior gravitational field, starting exclusively from the internal gradient of the density regarded as a scalar field.

1) Gravitational field and minimal potential

Let us consider a gravitational system with a non-uniform mass density, which provides an idealized model of a globular stars cluster of approximate radius R_o . The mass density is assumed to decrease linearly for $0 < r \leq R_o$:

$$\rho(r) = \rho_o(1 - r/R_o), \quad (74)$$

where ρ_o is a constant.

In this context, if we identify the scalar field $\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ with the mass density $\rho(\mathbf{x})$, and consider that, in the Newtonian limit $c \rightarrow \infty$, the minimal vector potential $\mathbf{Z}_o(\mathbf{x}, t)$ of representation (53) reduces to $\mathbf{Z}_o(\mathbf{x})$, then this potential may be associated with the gravitational field $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$, so that, according to Gauss's law,

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}) = \nabla \cdot \left[-\frac{\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})}{4\pi G} \right] = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{Z}_o(\mathbf{x}), \quad (75)$$

where G is the Universal Gravitational Constant.

Starting from the retarded representation (54) of the minimal vector potential \mathbf{Z}_o , and within the static configuration considered, by letting the gradient operator act on the integrand and performing an integration by parts, one obtains an expression that explicitly separates volume and boundary contributions, namely,

$$\mathbf{Z}_o = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_V dV' \frac{\nabla' \rho}{R} - \frac{1}{4\pi} \oint_S dS' \frac{\varphi_S}{R}. \quad (76)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{n}} = \hat{\mathbf{r}}'$ on the spherically symmetric boundary S . Since $\rho_S = \rho(R_o) = 0$, the surface integral vanishes, and only the volume contribution remains, evaluated over the source domain $r' \in [0, R_o]$. Accordingly, using the vector source $\nabla' \rho(r') = -(\rho_o/R_o) \hat{\mathbf{r}}'$, the minimal potential at a field point \mathbf{x} can then be written as

$$\mathbf{Z}_o(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{\rho_o}{4\pi R_o} \int_V dV' \frac{\hat{\mathbf{r}}'}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|}, \quad (77)$$

with $\mathbf{x}' = r' \hat{\mathbf{r}}'$, $dV' = r'^2 \sin\theta' dr' d\theta' d\varphi'$

For $r = |\mathbf{x}| > R_o$ y $\mathbf{x} = r\hat{\mathbf{z}}$, the expansion of the Green kernel,

$$\frac{1}{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|} = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{r'^l}{r^{l+1}} P_l(\cos\theta'), \quad (78)$$

in a series of Legendre polynomials, allows one to integrate over the azimuthal angle φ' . Then, projecting $\hat{\mathbf{r}}'$ onto $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ as $\hat{\mathbf{r}}' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}} = \cos\theta'$, the angular integral becomes

$$\int_0^\pi d\theta' P_l(\cos\theta') \cos\theta' \sin\theta' = \frac{2}{3} \delta_{l1}. \quad (79)$$

Therefore, with $\ell = 1$, the “minimal potential” is:

$$\mathbf{Z}_o = -\frac{\rho_o}{2R_o} \hat{\mathbf{z}} \int_0^{R_o} dr' \frac{r'^3}{r^2} \cdot \frac{2}{3} \quad \rightarrow \quad \mathbf{Z}_o(r) = -\rho_o \frac{R_o^3}{12r^2} \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \quad (80)$$

from which, by Gauss's law and definition (75), and considering spherical symmetry, the gravitational field for $r > R_o$ is:

$$\mathbf{g}(r) = 4\pi G \mathbf{Z}_o(r) = -\pi G \rho_o \frac{R_o^3}{3r^2} \hat{\mathbf{r}}. \quad (81)$$

The result obtained reproduces exactly the classical value of the gravitational field for a sphere with linearly decreasing density in the exterior region. This agreement is nontrivial: the minimal-gauge potential is determined by the spatial distribution of the density gradient inside the sphere, i.e. $\nabla\rho$ acts as the effective vector source.

It should be noted that if the scalar field $\varphi(\mathbf{x})$ is identified with a different physical quantity, then the minimal potential of that representation no longer reproduces an observable field and instead functions as a construct that links the vector source of the field with the global configuration of the system or with whatever boundary conditions have been imposed.

2) Gauge identities and Maxwell's Equations (\mathbf{D} , \mathbf{H})

In this application, we reconstruct the differential and functional forms of Maxwell's equations for the macroscopic electromagnetic fields (\mathbf{D} , \mathbf{H}) within the framework of the generalized Helmholtz theorem. This latter is applied to the scalar and vector potentials associated with Kapuścik's representation of these fields. In the resulting context of general potentials, the gauge relations that emerge upon extending the structure of the theorem's minimal differential identities acquire physical content when projected onto the macroscopic fields. Furthermore, a correspondence is established between these formulations and the effective physical sources associated with this pair of fields.

Given Kapuścik's representation (30) for the pair of electromagnetic fields (\mathbf{D} , \mathbf{H}), let us consider their associated vector potentials \mathbf{A} and $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ and apply to each of them the generalized Helmholtz decomposition in the form (12), written over all space under the physical assumption of localized sources and fields vanishing at infinity:

$$\mathbf{A} = -\nabla \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{D}'_A]}{4\pi R} + \nabla \times \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{C}'_A]}{4\pi R} + c^{-1} \partial_t \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{J}'_A]}{4\pi R}, \quad (82)$$

$$\mathbf{\Lambda} = -\nabla \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{D}'_\Lambda]}{4\pi R} + \nabla \times \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{C}'_\Lambda]}{4\pi R} + c^{-1} \partial_t \int dV' \frac{[\mathcal{J}'_\Lambda]}{4\pi R}. \quad (83)$$

Consequently, substituting Kapuścik's equations (30) into the corresponding vector source —the curl \mathcal{C}'_A and the time derivative \mathcal{J}'_A — of the decompositions (82) and, analogously for $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ in Ec. (83), performing the subsequent integrations by parts without introducing surface contributions, yields Helmholtz-type expressions

$$\mathbf{A} = -\nabla\phi_A + \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}_m - c^{-2} \partial_t \boldsymbol{\alpha}_e, \quad (84)$$

$$\mathbf{\Lambda} = -\nabla\phi_\Lambda - \varepsilon_o \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}_e - \varepsilon_o \partial_t \boldsymbol{\alpha}_m, \quad (85)$$

where the retarded scalar gauge functions

$$\phi_A = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[L'_A]}{R}, \quad \phi_\Lambda = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[L'_\Lambda]}{R}, \quad (86)$$

are defined in terms of L_A and L_Λ through Eq. (43), while the retarded Helmholtz integrals for each respective field, are given by

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_e = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_o} \int dV' \frac{[\mathbf{D}']}{R}; \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha}_m = \frac{\mu_o}{4\pi} \int dV' \frac{[\mathbf{H}']}{R}, \quad (87)$$

observing that, upon using the standard constitutive relations, the integrals in (87) contain as a particular case the contributions from the medium supported in the region V , which coincide with the classical Hertz potentials.[16][31]

Starting from expressions (84–85), the functions associated with the gauge constraints induced by the structure of the minimal identities (7), take, independently, the form

$$\mathfrak{D}_A := \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_m, \quad \mathbf{W}_A := -c^{-1}(\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}_e + \partial_t \boldsymbol{\alpha}_m), \quad (88)$$

$$\mathfrak{D}_\Lambda := -\epsilon_o \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_e, \quad \mathbf{W}_\Lambda := -\epsilon_o c (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}_m - c^{-2} \partial_t \boldsymbol{\alpha}_e). \quad (89)$$

If we now apply the differential operators belonging to $\mathfrak{D}_\alpha, \mathfrak{D}_\beta, \mathbf{W}_\beta$ and \mathbf{W}_α to the integrals (87) and integrate by parts, we reconstruct the integral expressions of the minimal potentials (34) to (36) as:

$$\mathfrak{D}_A = \mu_o \psi_o, \quad \mathbf{W}_A = \mu_o c \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_o; \quad (90)$$

$$\mathfrak{D}_\Lambda = -\epsilon_o \phi_o, \quad \mathbf{W}_\Lambda = -\epsilon_o c \mathbf{A}_o. \quad (91)$$

Noting that these potentials explicitly contain the Maxwellian functional expressions, and that the free and bound sources have support contained within the material region V , the Helmholtz gauge constraints $\mathfrak{D}_{A,\Lambda}$ and $\mathbf{W}_{A,\Lambda}$ become directly associated with the physical charge and current densities of the medium, in the form:

$$\mathfrak{D}_A = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_V dV' \frac{[\zeta'_m]}{R}, \quad \mathbf{W}_A = \frac{1}{4\pi c} \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathbf{I}'_m]}{R}; \quad (92)$$

$$\mathfrak{D}_\Lambda = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_V dV' \frac{[\rho'_e]}{R}, \quad \mathbf{W}_\Lambda = -\frac{1}{4\pi c} \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathbf{J}'_e]}{R}. \quad (93)$$

where the macroscopic equations (37) have been used.

Let us now consider the general scalar potential ϕ and ψ of Kapuścik's representation (30) for the macroscopic pair (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H}) . Treated as scalar fields $\varphi(\mathbf{x}, t)$, they admit a Helmholtz-type decomposition (60) over a finite region V with boundary S . Extension to all space requires additional decay conditions, not generally satisfied for potentials with $1/r$ asymptotic. Under these conditions, and using the sources in (56), we obtain

$$\phi = -\nabla \cdot \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathbf{G}'_\phi]}{R} + c^{-1} \partial_t \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathcal{J}'_\phi]}{R} + b.t._\phi, \quad (94)$$

$$\psi = -\nabla \cdot \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathbf{G}'_\psi]}{R} + c^{-1} \partial_t \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_V dV' \frac{[\mathcal{J}'_\psi]}{R} + b.t._\psi, \quad (95)$$

where $b.t._\phi$ and $b.t._\psi$ denote boundary terms. Substituting now Kapuścik's equations (30) into the vector sources corresponding to the gradients \mathbf{G}'_ϕ and \mathbf{G}'_ψ in (94-95), we obtain:

$$\phi = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_e + \partial_t \phi_A + b.t.'_\phi, \quad \psi = -\mu_o^{-1} \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_m + \partial_t \phi_\Lambda + b.t.'_\psi, \quad (96)$$

where $b.t.'_{\phi}$ and $b.t.'_{\psi}$ denote the boundary contributions arising from the above operations, and ϕ_A and ϕ_{Λ} are the retarded scalar gauge functions defined in Eq. (86). In the minimal gauge $L_A = L_{\Lambda} = 0$ —which in the present application corresponds to the usual Lorenz condition— these contribution vanish and the Helmholtz expressions (96) reduce to the constraints $\mathfrak{D}_{A,\Lambda}$, thus directly related to the physical scalar sources (ρ_e, ζ_m) .

In summary, this application shows that the gauge differential identities induced by the dynamical structure of the Helmholtz theorem not only preserve the macroscopic Maxwell differential combinations, but reproduce them functionally through the minimal potentials of the dual sector of the pair (\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{H}) . This crossed correspondence is a consequence of the internal coupling inherent in the Kapuścik representation. In turn, the scalar potentials (ϕ, ψ) admit a Helmholtz-type representation in terms of (α_e, α_m) , from which the minimal Lorenz gauge emerges as a particular case.

VI CONCLUSIONS

The Helmholtz theorem has been reformulated in terms of minimal potentials and the differential identities that arise from its structure. This framework provides a unified description for time-dependent scalar and dynamical vector fields in \mathbb{R}^3 , relating them to their effective sources and to the gauge sources that emerge within the formulation, thereby extending the scope of traditional integral decompositions.

A central result is that the minimal gauge reproduces, for more general potentials, the differential identities satisfied by the minimal potentials, ensuring the formal invariance of the representation. Moreover, the extension to pairs of coupled fields and its application to macroscopic electrodynamics show that the structure of identities induced by the generalized theorem not only reproduces the physical equations but also exhibits an internal dual correspondence between the minimal potentials of both sectors, preserving Maxwellian differential combinations.

The framework thus highlights the organizing role of differential identities in the formulation of massless fields with hyperbolic propagation in \mathbb{R}^3 , from which gauge structure consistently emerges.

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